

Consumer research domains in the sharing economy: An organising and categorizing review with research implications

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Abstract

This article presents a comprehensive systematic literature review (SLR) that organises and categorises consumer behaviour research in the context of the sharing economy. To structure the review, our review employs Hoyer et al.'s (2017) well-recognised consumer behaviour model, encompassing four dimensions and fourteen domains. Through a rigorous, transparent, and reproducible selection process, we identified 459 articles that delve into consumer behaviour within this field. Following a framework-based SLR approach, for each article, we meticulously examined its theoretical approach and results, including harmonious, contradictory, and inconclusive ones, assigning their contributions to the different dimensions and domains of consumer research. In addition, we highlight dimensions and domains that require further investigation, outlining directions, and gaps for future research. This systematic approach provides a comprehensive overview and insightful analysis of consumer behaviour in the sharing economy, facilitating a deeper understanding and offering valuable insights for scholars and practitioners in this field.

Keywords: access-based consumption, consumer behaviour, framework-based review, prosumer, sharing economy, systematic literature review

JEL codes: D16 · M13 · M31

1 Introduction

The sharing economy (SE) has become a sparkling business model, with a particular involvement of the end consumer, in its dual role of producer and consumer (C2C), and with a distinctive system of exchanges based on sharing and collaboration. The SE¹ constitutes one of the recent socioeconomic phenomena that have been of the most interest in the academic literature related to markets and consumption. Its disruptive nature, as technology-enabled socioeconomic system, has altered consumer norms and consumption notions (Li et al. 2024b). It involves a genuine combination of moral and market economies that has broken into many markets in a significant way, thanks to the "marketization of sharing" (Belk et al. 2019, p. 2).

Despite being an old practice, it has emerged as a novel and rapidly expanding reality (Khodayari et al. 2025), being currently considered as a 'nascent' area of research (Thornton 2024). Accordingly, there has been intense but scattered literature on SE and consumer behaviour (CB). This is a case between adjacent disciplines where it is useful to analyse and systematise the contributions because of their implications for both (MacInnis et al. 2019).

At the macro level, SE has implicated the market as innovation opposed to product innovation (Eckhardt et al. 2019) by expanding conventional boundaries with a new role for social resources (e.g., consumption, C2C interaction) and with the active role of technology (Perren and Kozinets 2018). Moorman et al. (2019, p. 1) describe SE as one of the phenomena that 'inspire research that pushes the current boundaries of marketing... that challenges assumptions in well-established areas of research... [that] force us to rethink three fundamentals of marketing: institutions (e.g., consumers, firms and channels, regulators), processes (e.g., innovation, brands, customer experience, value appropriation) and value creation (e.g., value for consumers, value for firms, value for society).' At the micro level, SE has entailed a new understanding of what consumption is, redefining it in light of its liquidity (Bardhi and Eckhardt 2017), shifting ownership as the centre of gravity of markets and consumers (Bardhi and Eckhardt 2012), emerging new consumer decision frameworks (Lamberton and Rose 2012), reporting new and different benefits in consumption (Li et al. 2024 [1]; McArthur 2014), and ultimately triggering new research questions about intrapersonal and interpersonal consequences on ways of consuming (Lamberton and Goldsmith 2020). Even the SE is proving to be particularly active in process and position innovations (Belezas and Daniel 2023). It is precisely the uncoupling of two traditionally linked cornerstones such as ownership and consumption (Bardhi and Eckhardt 2012) that is one of the key drivers of this new vision of consumption. CB literature proposes to replace the traditional view of legal ownership as the desired state of any

¹ For the sake of terminological simplicity, in the present work the term sharing economy encompasses all existing terms in the literature related to sharing and access-based consumption (e.g., access-based consumption, collaborative consumption, gig economy, etc.). A compilation of terms and definitions is listed in Sánchez-Pérez et al. (2021a).

consumer with a new view of ownership, understood as a continuum from simple access to ownership (Bardhi and Eckhardt 2017).

SE has involved a new system of product exchanges, use, and access modes that make up an innovative and distinctive socioeconomic system (Eckhardt et al. 2019). Furthermore, scholars regard technological innovation as a disruptive value that transforms the relationship between consumers and their goods (Morewedge et al. 2021). What implications has it had on CB research? The scope of the implications of the SE on CB research programmes is evident by the distinctiveness of sharing as a type of consumption (Belk 2010), the proposals of adaptations in the psychological concept of ownership (Morewedge et al. 2021), the proposal of a new institutional logic of the market economy dominated by sharing (Aspara and Wittkowski 2019), becoming consumers in providers (Wilhelms et al. 2017), an enhanced role of trust as core mechanism (Lee and Cha 2022) or distinctive consumer motivations (Chung et al. 2022). However, how have these questions impacted CB research programmes? How have these changes been implemented on the various processes and concepts of consumer behaviour? There is an open debate proposing a new research programme for the discipline that focusses on sharing (Lamberton and Goldsmith 2020). Indeed, SE has generated extensive research in the last decade, mostly multidisciplinary in nature (Belk et al., 2019), but significant in marketing and, specifically, CB (Aspara and Wittkowski 2019). Indeed, Sánchez-Pérez et al. (2021b) estimate that 28% of SE studies are related to CB.

Recent reviews of shared consumption have highlighted the diversity of theoretical approaches and the multifaceted effects of the collaborative economy on consumers, patterns, and relationships (Eckhardt et al. 2019; Khalek and Chakraborty 2023). Thus, compaction and reconciliation of scattered (and sometimes contradictory) results is needed, as revealed by the broad range of research questions posed to investigate (e.g., Khalek and Chakraborty 2023; Lamberton and Goldsmith 2020). Indeed, more recent contributions are examining the SE consumption behaviour in a more holistic way (e.g., Cappa et al. 2024). Thus, two main reasons may justify an integration of the sharing economy literature focused on the CB domains. First, there is an extensive literature on CB in the context of SE and needs examining. Second, the novelty and intensity of SE research have hindered us in focussing on identifying possible new topics and themes. In addition, the very complexity of CB as a discipline (e.g., Macinnis and Folkes 2010) has led to a fragmentation of studies in terms of substantive topics that require organising and categorizing, transforming previous disjoint and/or contradictory findings into more interwoven tapestry. Furthermore, an integrative literature review can be regarded as an interesting strategic pathway to theorization (Breslin and Gatrell 2023). Researchers need an integration of previously unconnected pieces of the

current SE-CB literature to draw conclusions about what is known, how this knowledge has been produced, and provide integrative guides to identify common themes and potential gaps (MacInnis 2011).

Therefore, the objectives of the present review are threefold. First, it aims to integrate SE's contributing pieces into the different domains of the CB discipline, accommodating extant knowledge to obtain a holistic and connected view of the contributions of SE related to CB. Second, find out the degree of development of each CB domain related to the SE field. And finally, identify potential research gaps to prioritise future research (Paul et al. 2021). To address these objectives, this study conducts a literature review inspired by the Breslin and Gatrell miner approach (2023), guided by the framework-based SLR (Paul and Criado 2020), adopting the recognised Hoyer et al.'s (2017) CB model.

2 Method

2.1 Selection of articles

We use the Web of Science (WoS) as data source because it is the research database with the longest history of article registration and citation (Birkle et al. 2020). Specifically, we used the *Web of Science Core Collection (Social Sciences Citation Index)* as a database to conduct this study. As preliminary exclusion criterion, we have decided not to include conference papers, books, and book chapters, since arguably encompass less validated knowledge (De Clercq et al. 2012). Likewise, similarly to other reviews, we excluded special issue editorials, review articles, and commentaries (Mishra et al. 2021).

Our selection process was then comprehensive and systematic (Fisch and Block 2018; Block and Fisch 2020; Clark et al. 2021). First, we searched for articles published during 1900–2024 that contained, in their title, abstract or keywords, the terms (1) 'sharing economy' or 'collaborative consumption' or 'collaborative economy' or 'peer-to-peer exchange' or 'peer-to-peer exchange' or 'P2P exchange' or "peer economy" or 'access economy' and (2) 'consumer *' or "consumption" or 'customer *' or 'client *' or "prosumer*" or 'societ*'. The selection of these keywords was made by reviewing previous articles and reviews that have addressed SE and CB independently (cf. Sánchez-Pérez et al. 2021a; Gupta et al. 2023) following a *scoping study* technique, as well as in the expertise of the authors. The search resulted in 1,759 articles. At this stage, as a second preliminary exclusion criterion and to focus on 'top-tier' journals, we have also decided to include only journals with an impact factor (IF) equal to or greater than 3.0. This procedure led to 1,308 articles. Second, as a suitability inclusion criterion procedure, three independent scholars read the title, abstract, and keywords of all articles to assess whether CB in the SE was a central rather than a peripheral theme within the studies. In case of doubts or disagreements as to whether an article

should be retained, a fourth investigator mediated until an agreement was reached (Clark et al. 2021). This step reduced the list of articles to 563.

Fig. 1 Articles selection procedure

Third, as a scope inclusion criterion procedure, three scholars independently reviewed the full articles to confirm that CB is a central topic within these studies. Once again, if disagreements emerged, a fourth researcher mediated until an agreement was reached. With this step, the final sample of 459 articles was reached (see all papers listed in Supplementary Material). Although the search started in 1900, the final sample of articles corresponds to the period 2015-2024, the most intense period of scientific production in SE, as confirmed by previous studies (Khalek and Chakraborty 2023). Figure 1 resumes the article selection procedure.

2.2 Analytic process

Framework-based reviews have shown a more robust structure than others reviews (Paul and Benito 2017). Then, we conducted this domain-based review to code articles according to a preset analytical framework.

Although this technique decontextualises the data to some extent, our objective is to provide a review focused on CB specifically, rather than all possible themes in SE research.

We draw on Hoyer et al.'s (2017) conceptual model for organising concepts and contributions. It is a worldwide reference in CB and use as landmark to exemplified consumer and marketing concepts (e.g., see Hardesty and Bearden 2009). Hoyer et al. (2017) identify four main dimensions of CB: (i) consumer culture, (ii) psychological core, (iii) consumer's decision-making process of consumer, and (iv) outcomes and issues. Hoyer et al. (2017) have additionally divided each dimension into various domains. In terms of consumer culture, we analyse how (i.1) social influences, (i.2) consumer diversity, (i.3) household and social class, and (i.4) psychographics affect CB. The psychological core is also divided into four domains: (ii.1) motivation, ability, and opportunity, (ii.2) from exposure to comprehension, (ii.3) memory and knowledge, and (ii.4) attitudes. Furthermore, to analyse the decision-making process, these authors suggest framing such studies in three themes: (iii.1) recognition and information search, (iii.2) judgment and decision-making, and (iii.3) post-decision processes. Finally, concerning consumer behaviour outcomes and issues, the Hoyer et al.'s (2017) framework suggests analysing (iv.1) innovation issues (that is, adoption, resistance, and diffusion), (iv.2) symbolic consumer behaviour and (iv.3) marketing, ethics, and social responsibility in today's consumer society. Then, based on the themes contained in each article, we coded it into one or more of the four dimensions and their respective domains. Figure 2 depicts the resulting distribution of articles and domains. We guarantee the rigour and transparency of the coding process using similar methods to those applied in the selection of articles stage, that is, three investigators independently coded the articles, and in case of discrepancies, a fourth investigator offered input until consensus emerged (Clark et al. 2021).

Fig. 2 Distribution of selected papers along the dimensions of the Hoyer et al.'s (2017) framework

3 Review of CB in the SE literature

Publications on the sharing economy began to grow strongly after the financial crisis of 2008, although those related to consumer behaviour began to flourish in 2015. Although it is a relatively new research field, the

Table 1. Articles and occurrence over time of dimensions and domains of CB in the SE literature

	Number of articles per dimension*	Domain	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	Number of articles per domain	
Dimension I The Consumer's Culture	184	1.1. Social influences			2	2	7	6	16	13	3	9	58	
		1.2. Consumer diversity	1	1	1	5	8	5	23	11	16	11	81	
		1.3. Household and social class			1		5	2	2	1	1		12	
		1.4. Psychographics	2	4	4	11	10	11	9	13	8	9	77	
Dimension II The Consumer's Psychological Core	384	2.1. Motivation, ability, and opportunity		3	9	14	19	21	28	37	26	24	181	
		2.2. From exposure to comprehension	2	7	7	14	17	19	31	32	24	27	173	
		2.3. Memory and knowledge			1	1	4	1	10	12	7	7	43	
		2.4. Attitudes	3	9	9	18	26	27	46	53	41	31	254	
Dimension III The Consumer's Process of Making Decisions	362	3.1. Problem recognition and information search			1	5	6	4	6	2	4	5	33	
		3.2. Judgment and decision making	5	13	13	23	31	35	46	48	35	35	271	
		3.3. Post-decision processes	1	3	3	6	13	14	18	27	19	18	119	
Dimension IV Consumer Behaviour Outcomes and Issues	147	4.1. Innovation issues	1	1	2	4	7	11	6	10	7	6	55	
		4.2. Symbolic consumer behavior							3	2	3	5	4	17
		4.3. Marketing, ethics, and social responsibility		2	1	7	9	13	12	15	9	14	82	
		1	20	54	110	162	172	255	277	205	200	Total		

* Some articles may be addressed to more than one dimension.

3.1 Dimension I: The Consumer Culture

3.1.1 Social influences

Several studies have examined the direct relationship between *social influence* and consumer behaviour intentions, finding mixed results. For example, while the studies by Oliveria et al. (2020) and Barnes et al. (2017) found that *social influence* is not associated with intentions to use SE platforms (SEPs), other studies find a positive influence of it on intentions to use SEPs (Min et al. 2018; Wang et al. 2019).

Other studies have explored the role of social influence in SE that accounts for how consumers are influenced by what they 'hear' other people say, such as electronic word-of-mouth (eWOM) and social interactions. Regarding the former, it has been found to increase perceived value and positively influence consumers' repurchase intention (Mao and Lyu 2017; Liang et al. 2017). In the case of studies that analyse social interactions, these assume that consumption of an individual is not usually independent of the consumption behaviour of others and, therefore, that social interaction is a 'social process of persuasion'. Shuqair et al. (2019) found that *social interactions* with the Airbnb host induce authenticity perceptions, which in turn have a positive impact on post-failure loyalty. Although with a slightly different approach, So et al. (2019) arrive at a similar finding, as they demonstrate that *social distance* negatively affects the loyalty towards Xiaozhu hosts. Delving into the study of

social distance, the study by Nguyen et al. (2020) emphasises that perceived social proximity increases trust in peers for collaborative services participants. The study by De Canio et al. (2020) demonstrates that *social esteem* has a positive impact on the intention to use Airbnb.

More recently the literature has highlighted concerns about climate change as a social influence and how environmental literacy affects collaborative consumption (Aktan and Kethüda 2024). The internationalisation of the SE phenomenon has led to the study of how cultural similarity affects the generation of opinions about experiences and different managerial response (Li et al. 2024a).

3.1.2 Consumer diversity

The articles reviewed on consumer diversity focused on analysing variables *such as age, generation, gender, education, and ethnicity*.

With respect to *age*, previous results show dissimilar findings. On the one hand, Prieto et al. (2017) show that age is a conditioning factor by demonstrating that older people are less likely to use car sharing. However, other researchers have not found any evidence that age is a relevant factor (Lutz and Newlands 2018; Ek-Styvén and Mariani 2020). Focussing on research on whether *generation* impacts CB in the SE, one study focused on the winning strategies for customer loyalty and argues that millennials seem to give preference to the ease and efficiency strategy (over interaction and online strategies), while baby boomers seem to represent more heterogeneous groups of customers (Akhmedova et al. 2020a). The study by Chang and Wang (2018) shows that although Z, Y, and X indicated the importance of online reviews for decision making when booking P2P accommodations, each generation assesses different aspects as the most relevant. Therefore, while Generations Z and Y paid more attention to reviews and cost, Generation X paid more attention to cleanliness and total stars.

Regarding gender, we found mixed results in different SE industries. In transportation, while Prieto et al. (2017) found that men are more likely to use P2P transportation services, Münzel et al. (2019) argued that gender does not have a significant difference. Alonso-Almeida (2019) further argues that women are more likely to use carsharing services when they perceive personal and business value in doing so. In the accommodation industry, studies show that women use shared rooms significantly less often than men (Lutz and Newlands 2018), and that they are more likely to book an Airbnb property hosted by a woman (gender congruity) (Su and Mattila 2020).

Regarding the education level of consumers, the studies of Prieto et al. (2017) and Münzel et al. (2019) agree that a higher education degree leads to a greater intention of adopting P2P transportation services. Furthermore, a study on the accommodation sector found that the higher the level, the higher the frequency of staying in an entire home on Airbnb; but that education does not influence the frequency of staying in a shared room (Lutz and

Newlands 2018). Concerning investigations on *ethnicity*, we only found the study of Ta et al. (2018), who found that an ethnic identity match between driver and consumer in the crowd-sourced delivery sector increases the level of trust, satisfaction, and repurchase intentions.

Cross-cultural studies are gaining attention, highlighting cross-cultural differences in the formation of perceptions of social trust, with the consequent divergence of platform trust (Cha and Lee 2022). These differences also extend to explaining the effects of physical attractiveness stimuli (i.e., digital material) on customer behaviour in SEPs (Ma et al. 2023). Also, as the SE becomes more widespread, it is of increasing interest to know the existence of differentiated behaviours in its use and satisfaction (Panniello et al. 2024).

3.1.3 Household and social class influences

Household and social class influences play a minimal role in the literature we reviewed. Although none of the papers refers to the term social class, they use variables such as *household income*, *spending*, *home location*, or *access to housing* as variables to create a social stratification. Three articles focus on the P2P accommodation sector, and we found that in two of them, income significantly influences CB. Mody et al. (2019b) found that people with lower income will have higher intentions to reuse and recommend Airbnb services if they perceive the experience to be memorable compared to those with higher income. Pappas (2019) suggested that income is an integral part of the price-quality nexus that influences the purchasing decisions. In another study, Volgger et al. (2019) hypothesised that spending is very strongly related to the use of P2P accommodation. In the P2P electricity trading sector, Hackbarth and Löbke (2020) found that people with lower income or those living in rented housing are more open to adopting this SE activity. Schleich et al. (2021) determine that savings explain the adoption of shared services, but suggest that occupiers as old as 70 years prioritize owning over renting.

Of the other three articles, two belong to the car-sharing sector. Münzel et al. (2019) found that household income does not have a significant influence on car sharing adoption. Another variable to explain car sharing adoption is found in the study of Prieto et al. (2017), where the authors show that people living in the city centre have a higher adoption of car sharing services compared to people living in the suburbs. In a study in another P2P sector, Makov et al. (2020) found that users associated with lower income are more able to participate in food waste reduction through SE.

3.1.4 Psychographics: values, personality, and lifestyles

The psychographic domain of consumer culture focuses on determining whether values, personality traits, and lifestyles affect CB in SE, and why consumer values, personality, and lifestyles change due to SE. The theme *values* demonstrate that emotional, social, functional, egoistic, altruistic, biospheric, hedonic, and utilitarian values

are important when analysing CB in the SE. Regarding *emotional values*, the study by Clauss et al. (2019) shows that positive emotions increase loyalty to SEPs. Expanding this vision, previous research has also shown that not only positive emotions positively affect consumer desire to adopt Airbnb services, but that negative anticipated emotions exert the same effect (Yi et al. 2020). Another study focused on *social value* argues that broader social values (e.g., promoting social equality) influence public acceptance of SE, such as promoting social equality; fostering the development of independent local communities; and promoting fair business practices (Cherry and Pidgeon 2018).

The literature has found dissimilar results on the role of *altruistic*, *biospheric*, and *egoistic values*. On the one hand, some scholars found that *altruistic* and *biospheric values* have a positive effect on the intention to participate in SE activities, while *egoistic values* have a negative impact (Roos and Hahn 2019). However, other researchers found that *egoistic value* has a positive relationship with intention to participate in SE activities and, in contrast, that *biospheric* and *altruistic values* do not influence on it (Becker-Leifhold 2018; Davlembayeva et al. 2020a). Lee and Kim (2018) also highlight the relevance of considering hedonic and utilitarian values, demonstrating that the hedonic value of consumers has a positive impact on satisfaction and loyalty, while the utilitarian value influences only the satisfaction of Airbnb consumers. Furthermore, the findings support those national cultural values, specifically being a collectivist and masculinist, positively affect consumer propensity and attitude of the consumer towards SE (Gupta et al. 2019; Ianole-Călin et al. 2020).

Articles regarding personality deal with factors such as whether consumers are materialistic, allocentric/psychocentric, open-minded, sociable, among others. Research in this group suggests that materialistic consumers are more likely to engage in second-hand SEPs (Parguel et al. 2017) and to participate in car sharing activities (Davidson et al. 2018). Moreover, based on differences in travel personality, Mody et al. (2019b) argue that allocentric (self-confident and intellectually curious) customers experience in a greater depth the SE accommodation experience landscape than psychocentric (nervous and non-adventurous) customers. In the same way, Juric et al. (2021) found that consumers who are open to experience have a greater intention to participate in the P2P accommodation sector, while consumers with a more conscious personality have a negative intention to do so. Furthermore, the literature argues that sociability plays an important role, acting as a direct antecedent of participation intention (Zhang et al. 2019).

Some studies have also found evidence that if consumers perceive that their *lifestyles* fit SE activities, they will be more likely to use them. Three empirical papers delve into this question. Hackbarth and Löbbe (2020) and Hahn et al. (2020) found that consumers whose lifestyle fits the idea of P2P electricity trading are more open

towards adopting it. In another study on the ride-sharing sector, Guyader (2018) identified three styles of sharing economy consumers, being one of those a group of individuals who seek access to ride-sharing due to a lifestyle with a commercial orientation.

More recently, researchers have turned their attention to the analysis of the social and experiential value of the SE (Heo and Kim 2024). So et al. (2022) have highlighted the importance of perceived social value, in addition to quality and functional value, in shaping attitudes towards sharing economy. However, Tajeddini et al. (2022), limit the role of social value in future consumer behaviour and suggest, instead, that self-gratification value leads to customer loyalty in SE.

It is worth noting that this domain incorporates the increasingly interesting issue of anti-consumerism, which affects the formation of trust in ride-sharing services, in particular, non-voluntary anti-consumerism (Lee and Cha 2022).

3.2 Dimension II: The Consumer s Psychological Core

3.2.1 Motivation, ability, and opportunity

Literature reports the major motivations for consumers to engage in SE activities: economic, social, and environmental (Milanova and Maas 2017). Economic motivations refer to expecting to get lower cost respect conventional companies (Lau et al. 2019; Dabbous and Tarhini 2019). Social motivation could arise from meeting, interacting and connecting with local communities (Tussyadiah and Pesonen 2015, 2016). Also, the environmental motivation arises from the assumption that SE activities are less resource intensive and thus help to reduce waste, minimising sustainability concern or even due to anti-consumption (Boukis et al. 2024 [8]; Gielens and Steenkamp 2019; Agag 2019). Anyway, these three types of motivations drive SE activities depending on the type of good or service (Gielens and Steenkamp 2019). In addition to sustainability, the abundant research on motives for using SE has looked at affective (Bosisio et al. 2024) and hedonic (Boukis et al. 2024) motivations behind people's participation in SE initiatives. Findings from two other investigations suggest that utilitarian motivation, hedonic motivation, price value, enjoyment, and home benefits also act as motivations that significantly explain behavioural intentions and attitudes towards SE practices (Wu et al. 2017b; So et al. 2018). Other non-commercial benefits such as altruism and social utility have been added (Say et al. 2021). Personal factors can also affect motivations (Hoyer et al. 2017). Specifically, wealthier and younger customers can be more socially motivated (Davlembayeva et al. 2020b), and risk perception can shape consumer's attitude towards the SE, which results in lower intentions to use it (e.g., Lee et al. 2018; Hawlitschek et al. 2018; Shao and Yin 2019; Day et al. 2020; Lee 2020).

Another dimensions that include this theme has to do with consumer opportunity and ability. Concerning the former, Chameroy et al. (2024) find that interchangeability between buyer and seller facilitates trust in SEPs. For the latter, based on the theory of planned behaviour (TPB), perceived behavioural control (PBC) is considered as a fundamental trait for consumers' intentions to share services (Kim et al. 2018; Hawlitschek et al. 2018). Additionally, consumers with higher cognitive ability (e.g., environmental literacy) and emotional push have a natural predisposition to prefer co-ownership and leasing solutions (Aktan & Kethüda 2024 [33]; Aspara and Wittkowski 2019). The second of these analyses share aids (as an emotional resource) and argue that share aids increase the intention to use a car-sharing service (Oyedele and Simpson 2018). To conclude this subsection, it remains to be argued that we have identified only one article that focusses on analysing opportunity within the core psychological of the consumer. Specifically, the study by Amirkiaee and Evangelopoulos (2018) evidences that the expectation of time benefit leads to the formation of attitudes toward ride sharing.

3.2.2 From exposure to comprehension

SE perceptual stimuli have been proposed as determinants of consumers' cognitive responses. Even the experience of value co-creation in the SE was linked as a consumer stimulus (Nadeem and Salo 2024).

Initially, contributions have focused on platform stimuli. Thus, social presence and confirmation increase perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use (Ye et al. 2019; Shao et al. 2020), as these two perceptions facilitate comprehension of the SE and push to engage in sharing activities (Barnes and Mattsson 2017; Liang et al. 2019; Juric et al. 2021). Other two variables that have received attention are perceived value (Chen and Chang 2018) and perceived authenticity (Shuqair et al. 2019).

Since much of exposure to stimuli in the SE takes place when the consumer is browsing SEPs, perceiving through vision has been addressed by scholars as the main sensory stimulus. The aesthetics (Xu and Schrier 2019; Akarsu et al. 2020), perceived platform qualities (Lee et al. 2018), or the physical attractiveness of digital stimuli (Ma et al. 2023), influence visual perception and preferences. In particular, hosts' facial expression on photos increase consumer's booking intention (Han et al. 2024), but it also play an additional role, enhancing perceived trustworthiness of sellers (Ert et al. 2016; Ta et al. (2018) find that perceived similarity (through vision) is a primary mechanism through which SE disclosure designs impact outcomes. Recently, the study of sensory stimuli in SE has been extended to physical contexts such as the hospitality sector (Radic et al. 2024). In the post-purchase phase, a good feeling of home has been shown to stimulate better ratings (Kumar 2024).

3.2.3 Memory and knowledge

Memorability experiences play a critical role in SE tourism and hospitality (Li et al. 2023). Few articles have addressed the domain of memory and knowledge. Studies have mainly studied what factors influence the memorability of formation (the creation of memorable experiences) and the outcomes of such memorability. Extraordinary results (Mody et al. 2017), well-being (Mody et al. 2019a), pleasure and arousal (Mody et al. 2019c), and features of the trip (e.g. customer involvement, length of stay, or price) (Mody et al. 2019b) have been found to positively influence the memorability of the P2P accommodation experience. On the knowledge aspect, Hackbarth and Lbbecke (2020) posits that a higher level of consumer knowledge will lead to an increase in purchase intention. Similarly, knowledge about SE has positive effects on the level of participation in the sharing market (Gazzola et al. 2019). Further, the intimate brand knowledge has been identified as determinant of use luxury brands through access-based means of consumption (Kumar 2024).

3.2.4 Attitudes

Consumer attitudes play a central role in the CB literature, being a prominent topic is SE behavioural intentions. Basically, studies on this subject can be divided into two main thematic blocks: on the one hand, studies that have focused on explaining formation of consumer attitudes in the SE, and on the other, studies focused on explaining the impact of consumer attitudes on CB. Of all the attitudes in this domain, trust is a key construct. Often incorporated into CB models through the Theory of Planned Behaviour (Ajzen 1991) and the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) (Davis 1989) papers aimed at explaining the formation of trust (e.g., Park and Tussyadiah 2020a) represent a significant share of papers. Although the formation of consumer trust vary from industry to industry (e.g., accommodation, ride-sharing) (Barnes and Mattsson 2017; Shao and Yin 2019), scholars have identified as determinants of trust (Park and Tussyadiah 2020b), integrity, ability, benevolence (Agag and Eid 2019), social presence (Ye et al. 2019), personal innovativeness (Wang and Jeong 2018), transaction safety (Kong et al. 2020), support (Ahn 2024), social referrals, information quality, and social distance (Nguyen et al. 2020).

Taken as a whole, institutional trust towards the SE as a community is a key antecedent of purchase intentions (Lu and Yi 2023). Specific dimensions of trust have also been commonly studied. For example, trust in others (Hartl et al. 2018), affective trust (Su and Mattila 2020), trust in SEPs (Lee et al. 2018; Ye et al. 2019; Park and Tussyadiah 2020b), trust in the sharing partner (Mittendorf et al. 2019), trust in the driver (Shao and Yin 2019), trust in the provider (Day et al. 2020), trust in the service (Liang et al. 2019), and interpersonal trust (Ma et al. 2020), have been found as factors influencing the consumer's intention to use P2P sharing. Attitudes towards SE

have also been focus of attention. Contributions show that customer attitudes towards these SE activities influence the intention to adopt car-sharing services (Hartl et al. 2018, Zhu et al. 2017), and the intention of sustainable use in the context of bike-sharing practices (Si et al. 2020). Furthermore, it has been found that attitude towards SE positively influences the intention to use sharing services (Bucher et al. 2016; Oliveira et al. 2020), SEP (Delgosha and Hajiheydari 2020), and shared consumption behaviour (Roos and Hahn 2019).

Another variable that has received significant attention is the attitude towards SE behaviour, adopted from TPB. These are made up of monetary, moral, and social hedonic motives (Bucher et al. 2016). Consumers' attitudes toward the adoption of SE services are shaped by personal beliefs, such as cost savings, efficient use of resources, community with others (Roos and Hahn 2019), knowledge and social aspect (Dabbous and Tarhini 2019), awareness of the sharing economy (Kim et al. 2018), or consumer minimalism (Shukla et al. 2024). Specifically, research has investigated how personal traits explain attitudinal loyalty in SE services (Lee and Wong 2021). Focussing on guest attitudes to P2P accommodation, researchers argue that these are formed by perceived usefulness (Wang and Jeong 2018), subjective norms, perceived value, unique experience (Mao and Lyu 2017), perceived risks and benefits (Lee 2020), environmental concerns, subjective norm, and awareness of consequences (Agag 2019). Most recently, ethical practices (Nadeem et al. 2023), environmental and sustainability issues have gained interest as determinant of customers' intentions (Huang et al. 2024). In the car sharing and ride-sharing sector, perceived corporate social responsibility (Jeon et al. 2020), relative advantage and compatibility (Hahn et al. 2020), or the self-efficacy of the app (Zhu et al. 2017) are determined to be factors that influence consumers' attitudes towards using it.

3.3 Dimension III: The consumer decision-making process

3.3.1 Problem recognition and information search

In the context of our review, few articles address problem recognition and information search. This is surprising, since it is the first step of the decision-making process for SE consumers (Wirtz et al. 2019) and, therefore, it is relevant for the rest of the decision-making process. Indeed, the interactivity between users and providers enhances customer engagement on SEPs (Yuan et al. 2024).

One of the relevant issues to be addressed within this domain is what kind of information is acquired in external search by consumers? In answering this question, it must be borne in mind that SEPs could try to limit knowledge of previous users' experience to only congruent and positive information (Stough and Carter 2023). The review of literature from different SE sectors (e.g., ridesharing, accommodation, second-hand clothing) indicates that consumers acquire information on topics such as personal reputation (Mauri et al. 2018), product

descriptions (Nisar et al. 2020), environmental issues (Day et al. 2020), offer duration (Jang et al. 2021), rating volume, information quality, media richness (Chen and Chang 2018), private messaging service, visual representations, counterparty biographical information (McDaid et al. 2019), and reviews (Camacho-Otero et al. 2019). In addition, the COVID-19 pandemic has prompted public information of safety, sanitation and cleanliness procedures (Godovykh et al. 2023).

As the P2P sector relies on reputation systems, online reviews and, in general, word-of-mouth (WOM) practices, are a critical source of information for both providers and consumers (Lee 2022). A number of studies have addressed what determines the search for information through online reviews. For example, the study by Dann et al. (2020) shows that text reviews affect information search and booking intentions both through economic and social value expectations in a P2P accommodation. Furthermore, the availability of a host self-description and an excellent star rating affect information search and booking intentions through consumer social value expectations and consumers' economic value expectations, respectively. Camacho-Otero et al. (2019) further argue that online reviews provided significant information on economic factors and the impacts this type of offering has on users. Chang and Wang (2018) shows that emotions expressed in reviews influence information search and consumer decisions, and negative reviews are more likely than positive reviews to affect them.

Another important issue to address in this domain is what attract consumers to start or continue an external search? Although few studies have focused on addressing this issue, an exception is the work of Xu and Schrier (2019) arguing that perceived aesthetics, perceived ease of navigation, perceived information quality, familiarity, and perceived privacy positively impact external search intention. The other exception is the study developed by Bae and Koo (2018) in which the authors show that in a normal environment (when ratings are high), visualisers (verbalisers) have more of an external search intention when they are exposed to abundant pictures (textual cues). However, when the cues lead to a further information search (when the ratings are low), this search behaviour pattern is reversed.

3.3.2 Judgment and decision making

Of the fourteen domains of the Hoyer et al.'s (2017) conceptual model, this one has received the most attention. It should be noted that judgment and decision-making are two interrelated processes in which the consumer's evaluations or estimates (judgments) inform the behavioural intention, willingness, or propensity to pursue a course of action among alternatives (decision making). As a prerequisite, it is argued that intention, willingness, or propensity to participate in sharing activities depends on whether exchange mechanisms and the consumption or service contexts do match (Küper and Edinger-Schons 2020).

As intentions represent the rationale for selecting a specific action among alternatives, this is the most common analysed variable. Based on TPB, variables that have received relative attention due to their impact on behavioural intentions are subjective norm, PBC, and attitudes. There exists generally harmonious evidence that the subjective norm (i.e., individual's judgment about a particular behaviour) predicts the intention to adoption of SE activities (Hawlitschek et al. 2018; Roos and Hahn 2019; Sakib et al. 2023 [67]). Indeed, these findings are consistent across a variety of sectors, in which the authors find that subjective norm influences the intention to book an SE accommodation (over a hotel) (So et al. 2018; Agag 2019), to rent clothes (over buying them) (Becker-Leifhold 2018), to use a parking space sharing system (over a traditional parking space) (Liang et al. 2019), or to use a bike sharing system (over using non-sustainable transport systems) (Si et al. 2020). From a social perspective, self-disclosure dynamics help to increase trust in service provider and reduce perceived risk (Tran et al. 2022).

Regarding PBC, several studies (e.g., Hawlitschek et al. 2018; Ianole-Călin et al. 2020) suggest that it influences behavioural intention to consume collaboratively (overconsuming traditional services and products). In fact, scholars argue that PBC is one of the strongest predictors of the intention to collaboratively consume in three sectors, park sharing (Liang et al. 2019), bike sharing (Si et al. 2020), and clothing rental (Becker-Leifhold 2018). The third variable, attitudes, has also been suggested as a predictor of intention to use sharing services (over traditional services) by several investigations (Dabbous and Tarhini 2019; Oliveira et al. 2020). Again, some studies confirm that these results remain stable in various sectors of the SE (e.g. accommodation (Bucher et al. 2016; Toni et al. 2018; Agag 2019; Lee 2020), park sharing (Liang et al. 2019), bike sharing (Si et al. 2020), and clothing rental (Becker-Leifhold 2018).

Personal norms have also received some consideration, although to a lesser extent. Studies that have addressed this variable argue that personal norms strongly influence the intention of collaborative consumption (Kim et al. 2018; Ianole-Călin et al. 2020). The rationale for these arguments is to expect consumers carefully evaluate whether SE as a 'new' form of consumption is the 'right or wrong thing to do'. Another judgment factor that informs behavioural intentions towards engaging in sharing activities is consumer trust (Dabbous and Tarhini 2019). We find contradictory results in the car-sharing sector. On the one hand, Lee et al. (2018) argue that trust exerts a positive effect on the intention to participate in car-sharing. On the other hand, the study by Barnes and Mattson (2017) shows that the intention to rent a carsharing is not influenced by the trust of the consumer. The results of the second study are ratified in the fashion sector, as the findings of Day et al. (2020) evidence that trust in the product service system is not positively related to behavioural intention. Due to the COVID-19 pandemic, cleanliness information has been incorporated as another determinant of consumer trust (Godovykh et al. 2023).

Disclosure of information can create a positive impression on consumers, but too much information may generate opposite effects (Xu et al. 2021). Undoubtedly, one issue that influences consumer decision-making is the evaluation they make of the cost-benefit ratio between the different alternatives. In the SE fashion sector, the findings suggest that the perceived cost-benefit value influences the purchase intention of a branded fashion subscription of a product service system (Day et al. 2020). This means that if the consumer believes that he/she will save money, he/she will be more likely to consume these products rather than using a traditional business model.

In the P2P accommodation sector, behavioural intentions towards home-sharing platforms are influenced by profit benefits such as economic appeal (Tussyadiah and Pesonen 2016) or cost savings (Wu et al. 2017b). In addition, other economic aspects that affect price evaluation have also been investigated. For example, the study by Lutz and Newlands (2018) argues that socioeconomic status influences the decision-making of consumers when they have to decide to rent either shared rooms or entire home. The investigation by Olya et al. (2018) finds that income levels negatively influenced the behavioural intentions of disabled tourists to use P2P accommodations.

Another relevant aspect studied within this domain is the repeated purchase of an SE service. It should be noted that there are several terms that denote these repeat purchase intentions, such as repurchase, revisit, reuse, loyalty, continued use, and future intentions to choose. According to some studies, loyalty is achieved through various consumer judgments such as quality of service, customer value (Akhmedova et al. 2020b), the intersection of website/app organisation, platform responsiveness and reliability, and customer interaction with peer service provider (Akhmedova et al. 2020a).

Boateng et al. (2019) found that trust, customer return on investment, and search convenience are key factors that contribute to riders' re-usage of Uber service. In the case of ridesharing, Shao and Yin (2019) note the importance of trust in the driver and in the SEP for the intention to continue. Finally, in the P2P accommodation sector, we find a wider diversity of studies that have addressed this topic. Judgments such as the memorability of the experience (Mody et al. 2017), likeability (Akarsu et al. 2020), attitudes, satisfaction (Wang and Jeong 2018), user attachment (Yang et al. 2019), subjective norms (Mao and Lyu 2017), enjoyment, monetary benefits (Tussyadiah 2016), eWOM, unique experience expectation, familiarity (Mao and Lyu 2017), and spatial distance (So et al. 2019) influence consumers future intentions to repeat P2P accommodation.

It should be noted that a number of other variables have been analysed, albeit in isolation, in relation to the explanation of consumer judgement and decision making. Among these, we can highlight that the following categories explain the intention to consume collaboratively: social appeal-related variables (De Canio et al. 2020),

service performance (Akbar 2019), and affective traits (Zhang et al. 2018). It should be noted that two studies argue that environmental concerns play a key role when consumers make decisions about using P2P services over B2C services, in the way that environmentally conscious consumers are more likely to be tempted to use P2P platforms (Parguel et al. 2017; Hartl et al. 2018).

Finally, a minor body of literature has focused on identifying factors that negatively influence consumer decision making. Specifically, these are uncertainty avoidance and power distance (Gupta et al. 2019), some host patterns (e.g., response rate of the host) in the accommodation sector (Wu et al. 2017a), transaction utility of ownership, perceived product scarcity risk in the car-sharing sector (Akbar 2019), perceived physical condition risk, perceived shopping opportunities risk, and perceived return liability risk on the clothing rental sector (Day et al. 2020), and negative P2P experiences and peers-to-platform experiences (Grüner et al. 2024).

3.3.3 Post-decision processes

Satisfaction and loyalty are the most analysed post-decision processes. Concerning the latter, researchers have focused on determining the various factors that impact consumer satisfaction, creating a positive influence on satisfaction by sharing intention, user behaviour, trust, smartphone capability, economic benefits, and user ethical perceptions (Oliveira et al. 2020). Service quality has been shown to be a significant predictor of customer satisfaction (Lim et al. 2021). In the accommodation sector, an in-depth analysis developed by Ju et al. (2019) finds that SE accommodation owns multiple service quality attributes associated with website, host, and facility that produce distinctive effects on guest satisfaction. Other studies that analysed this sector extend these results by demonstrating that customer satisfaction with SE accommodation stay is affected by accommodation amenities, host-guest relationship (Wang and Jeong 2018), enjoyment, monetary benefits (Tussyadiah 2016), good communication, large space, provision of information about environment (Zhu et al. 2019), perceived trust (Lu et al. 2020), perceived authenticity, safety, and security risk (Birinci et al. 2018). In addition, different types of values such as hedonic, utilitarian, functional, economic, emotional, social, and ethical values (Lee and Kim 2018; Jiang et al. 2019) have also been found to be predictors of guest satisfaction. The impact on service quality is highlighted by the service recovery approaches implemented by providers (Chen and Tussyadiah 2021). However, only a few papers have studied the effects of satisfaction on consumers' future behaviour, such as Oliveira (2020) and Lim et al. (2021).

A few articles study some “responses” to satisfaction as post-decision processes such as intention to recommend, WoM, loyalty, and high (low) rating. For example, literature argues that likeability influences consumers' intention to recommend SE accommodation (Akarsu et al. 2020) and that trust increases positive

WOM. A spillover effect has also been identified, where a negative review of the consumer by the peer (Grüner et al. 2024) or from the provider leads to negative WOM about the platform (Rifkin et al. 2023). Regarding loyalty, also a significant which is recognised as a clear response to consumer satisfaction, the studies show that loyalty is achieved at the intersection of website/app, platform responsiveness and reliability, and customer interaction with the peer service provider (Akhmedova et al. 2020a), and that brand love has a significant and positive impact on brand loyalty (Mody and Hanks 2020). Sustainability has become a driver of loyalty, especially for young users (Garrod et al. 2023). Lee et al. (2024) find that different configuration of services ('recipes') can be designed to enhance loyalty, differentiating between attitudinal and behavioural loyalty.

Additionally, it is worth to mention that artificial intelligence techniques are entering the SE literature because of their interest and potential to identify problems in SEPs and adjust mechanisms to optimise the customer experience (Eckhardt et al. 2019).

3.4 Dimension IV: Consumer behaviour outcomes and issues

3.4.1 Innovation issues: Adoption and resistance

This dimension is the least developed. It should be noted that access-based consumption has been innovative in incorporating prosumer-driven processes along with a different consumer context, by empowering and motivating consumers to contribute to the productive and marketing functions, developing an own customer journey (Trujillo-Torres et al. 2024).

Relatively few studies examine the adoption and resistance despite the fact that innovation is a key aspect of SE. It has been observed that service improvements and innovations can come from users who are grateful for the experience they received (Chou et al. 2023). As the SE is a technological disruption, the technological component plays a crucial role in consumer acceptance (Cappa et al. 2024). And although the SE is a new concept, it does not mean that all the innovations related to its use have been incorporated. For example, there is some resistance to paying with cryptocurrency (Loh et al. 2023). On the one hand, regarding adoption, some studies have shown that several factors facilitate the adoption intention of service innovations offered by the SE. For example, studies of Delgosha and Hajiheydari (2020) and Zhu et al. (2017) suggest that consumer attitudes toward adopting on-demand SEPs increase their adoption intention. Also, the perceived usefulness is positive related to consumer adoption as it is the case of parking services (Liang et al. 2019). Yin et al. (2019) investigation focused on the bike sharing sector also shows that a positive WOM improves the reputation and legitimacy of SE firms and encourages non-users to adopt SE service innovations becoming bike-sharing users.

On the other hand, another set of articles have suggested various barriers that make consumers reluctant to adopt SE services innovations. Delgosha and Hajiheydari (2020), for example, find that reasons against adopting on-demand service platforms will reduce consumer adoption intentions and that, indeed, these reasons against negatively moderate the relationship between reasons for and adoption intention. Focussing on the accommodation sector, Juric et al. (2021) propose that low perceived usefulness and risk of technology use have a negative effect on the intention of adoption. Two other studies, focused on the car-sharing and bike-sharing sectors, suggest as reasons for the non-adoption of these services the accessibility to own transportation, the lack of information about the option, and negative WOM (Yin et al. 2019; Münzel et al. 2019).

3.4.2 Symbolic consumer behaviour

Symbolic CB represents the type of purchase that occurs when consumers buy a specific good or service because of what it means, based on the symbols attributed to it by society. Among these, it is the study developed by Fritze et al. (2020), which states that SE consumers use the services they offer as identity-related symbols and also take advantage of their symbolic meaning to avoid unwanted identities. Another research in this domain argues that some consumers use SEs because they believe that they help social inclusion and subjective well-being (Davlembayeva et al. 2020a). The study developed by Jeon et al. (2020) shows that consumer brand attitude and self-brand connection with Uber make consumers to have a brand preference for a special brand, as they see themselves reflected in Uber in a symbolic way.

Although a few articles focused their attention on this domain, different trends with special symbolism can be observed. In the travel industry, the SE is developing authentic peer-to-peer tourism service exchanges, supported on P2P platforms (Kromidha et al. 2023). Driven by hedonism (Christodoulides et al. 2021), brands of special symbolism and intimate knowledge such as luxury brands are redefining shifts in consumption towards renting or borrowing as opposed to buying (Kumar 2024). This is the case with the formal swapping of clothes, which has become a symbol of the identity of NextGen (Armouch et al. 2024).

3.4.3 Marketing, ethics, and social responsibility in today's consumer society

The SE has raised a number of issues in this area. Regarding consumer ethics, Ma et al. (2020) show that customer civility is a concept established in ethical consumption in the SE and finds that interpersonal trust, property experience, and platform governance are antecedents of customer civility in the P2P accommodation sector. More recently, at the ethical level, on the one hand, ethical marketing influence consumers' willingness to pay SE services (Nadeem et al. 2023). On the other, several researchers have looked into the dark behaviour of

users who deliberately bypass the payment process of the platforms to deal directly with the providers in order to save money (Nguyen et al. 2024).

Some scholars argue that SE is a type of anti-consumption movement that encompasses ethical and social responsibility consumption (see, e.g., Hüttel et al. 2020). These include the desire to foster social equality, in relation to both the opportunity and benefits promised by the sharing economy; encourage and support the development of strong and independent local communities; and ensure that business practices operate fairly in the shared interest of business, consumers, and the environment (Cherry and Pidgeon 2018). In this regard, several proxy variables are used to study anti-consumption, consumer ethics, and environmentally conscious behaviour in the SE. Regarding anti-consumption, two studies find that it is not a significant driver to SE usage intentions. In the first one, it is shown that anti- is not a reason for consumers to have better attitudes towards P2P sharing (Hawlitsek et al. 2018). Another study shows that consumer's anti-consumption disposition has no influence on the intention to choose an SE offer (Akbar and Hoffmann 2018).

Concerning environmentally conscious behaviour, contributions identify several drivers that influence sustainable consumption behaviours in SE. Specifically, sustainable development and ecological sustainability benefits (Gazzola et al. 2019; De Canio et al. 2020), ascription of responsibility (Kim et al. 2018), the intention to use SE services (Toni et al. 2018), moral obligation (Si et al. 2020), social influence (Wang et al. 2019), perceived CSR (Jeon et al. 2020), positive attitude towards the environment and production transparency (Hackbarth and Löbbe 2020), concerns about green consumption (Hartl et al. 2018), and green morality (Shang and Wu 2022) influence sustainable consumption behaviours in SE. Reciprocally, it has also been suggested that homestays tourism stimulates sustainable behaviours through psychological ownership (Kumar and Chandra 2024). However, all these conclusions contradict with three papers that argue that social responsibility issues related to environmentally conscious behaviour do not influence intentions to participate in SE activities. For example, Akbar and Hoffmann (2018) investigation find that environmental consciousness does not influence the decision to use an SE offer. Similarly, Si et al. (2020) propose that awareness of consequences does not play a significant role in the intention of sustainable use. Furthermore, other studies argues that perceived sustainability negatively affects satisfaction in guest accommodation (Tussyadiah 2016).

Another sector that has received significant attention in this topic is the buying or renting of second-hand clothing. Peña-Vinces et al. (2020) found that environmental knowledge and parents' previous experience in the SE condition their willingness to behave responsibly by buying or renting second-hand. Parguel et al. (2017) investigation show that environmentally conscious consumers possess cognitive dissonance reduction and

indulgent consumption in the context of second-hand P2P platforms. At a certain point, on the contrary, the study of Day et al. (2020) shows that environmental-related product information influences consumer perceived environmental benefit value, but that perceived environmental benefit value does not influence SE purchase intention. Finally, Herold and Prokop (2023) suggest that collaborative clothing schemes depend on consumers' style and sustainability desires.

4 Research agenda

As a business model that facilitates people to transact directly with one another, our research began with the analysis of SE research related to the various working domains of consumer behaviour. Overall, user-centred studies on SE exhibit an imbalance in favour of understanding internal consumption and decision-making processes, as opposed to external processes and the outcomes of decisions taken. Cultural characteristics appear to have a lower impact on experiential consumption in the SE industry than situational factors, whereas research focused on psychographics has not achieved conclusive results on the role of values on SE engagement. We also find contradictory and inconclusive findings regarding the role of social influences and consumer diversity on SE consumption, and always mediated by the type of industry. Relevant research activity has focused on the *psychological core* dimension, producing typologies of SE-specific motives and segmentation schemes. The interest generated by planned behaviour and self-determination theories have also become apparent. Other salient themes in this domain are consumer perceptions and attitudes. Specifically, existing research reveals that consumer trust and attitudes toward SE consumption are critical to understanding of consumer choice. However, since contributions have only been partial, a holistic approach is needed to truly understand the characteristics that influence perception formation and considerations related to consumer memorability. Consumer psychological core research, addressing *judgment and decision-making processes*, evidences that personal norms and, especially, trust, play a key role in consumer decisions. However, the type of information acquired in external search by the consumers, or what attracts consumers to start or continue an external search, still remain unclear.

The least developed domains have to do with the fourth dimension, *consumer behaviour outcomes, and SE specific issues*. Contributions are limited and no conclusive evidence can be found specifically on this consumer dimension, though it has increased recently due to research interest in ethical issues and anti-consumption. Considering that innovation issues are key to the growth of the SE, this lack of attention on the part of researchers is striking. and social responsibility (e.g., environmental consciousness) have contradictory and inconclusive results with respect to their relationship with intentions to engage in sharing activities (Toni et al. 2018). It is remarkable that this domain needs to be investigated, insofar as there is a growing social and political interest in

the sharing economy with new concerns arising due to the emergence of the AI. There are a wide number of domains and areas of consumer behaviour related to the sharing economy that require further research. Table 2 lists a number of issues identified in the review that are of particular interest and require further research (Table 2).

Table 2. Main research gaps of SE related to CB

Dimension	Domain	Research gap
Dimension I: The customer's culture	Social influences	The role of influencers to provide social proofs and build P2P connections (Liang et al. 2017)
		New perspectives on conceptualizing consumption of the sharing economy (e.g. sustainability, lifestyle, social movements) (Cheng 2016)
	Consumer diversity	Effects of cultural similarity on SE experiences (Li et al. 2024a)
		Are individual characteristics valid criteria to explain differences in sharing economy service preferences? (Chang and Wang 2018, Parker et al. 2019).
		Delve into how the cultural and ethnicity group influences SE consumption (e.g., agentic vs. communal goals) (Ta et al. 2018)
Household and social class	Cross-cultural variations in SE consumption (Lutz and Newlands 2018)	
	Understand different effects of stimuli of SE use (Ma et al. 2023)	
Psychographics	Differentiating SE decision process by segments (Guttentag et al. 2017; Schleich et al. (2021) [222])	Influence of the family life cycle and household decision roles in SE consumption (Prieto et al. (2017)
		How can values influence collaborative consumption? (Ta et al. 2018)
	Is travelling through the sharing economy a lifestyle? (Paulauskaite et al. 2017)	Social value of the SE (Heo and Kim 2024)
		Relationship between anti-consumption and SE (Lee and Cha 2022)
Dimension II: The consumer's psychological core	Motivation, ability, and opportunity	Are motivations to use P2P platforms a differential advantage of SE? (Guttentag et al. 2017)
		What conditions customers may wish to engage in co-creation in collaborative consumption (Benoit et al. 2017)
		Effects of environmental literacy on access-based solutions (Aktan and Kethüda 2024)
	From exposure to comprehension	Affective and hedonic motivations to engage in the SE initiatives (Boukis et al. 2024; Bosisio et al. 2024)
		Do consumers make inferences from the most relevant SE brands (e.g., Airbnb, Uber, Lyft)?
		Are SE and non-SE services perceived as similar? (Mody et al. 2017)
		How SE marketing stimulus (i.e., information and media) impact on consumers' comprehension of stimuli (Chen and Chang 2018, Ert et al. 2016, Xu and Schrier 2019)
Memory and knowledge	How does the information for SE become salient within the minds of consumers over time? (Chen and Chang 2018)	
	Impact of alternative digital stimuli on consumer's booking intention (Han et al. 2024)	
	Recognition and recall of SE product experiences (Wu et al. 2017b)	
The role of SE in the associative network of concepts related to product categories (Mody et al. 2019b)	Branding strategies in SE products (Wirtz et al. 2019)	
	What are the prototypical brands like in the SE? (Mody et al. 2019a)	

		How are the SE solutions implemented in the memory schemes?
	Attitudes	Do positive attitudes towards SE translate into effective consumption? (Hamari et al. 2016) How do normative influences encourage trust and SE consumption? (Park and Tussyadiah 2020b) Do products from the sharing economy have the same potential to activate positive emotions? (Ert et al. 2016) How does environmental consciousness interact with personal cost-saving preferences? (Lee and Wong 2021)
	Problem recognition and information search	Information acquired in an external search: platforms vs. no platforms (Bae and Koo 2018) Better understanding of consumer decision processes related to SE in the online community (Dann et al. 2020) Is there a need for additional public consumer information? Is there a need for additional public consumer information, as was the case with COVID-19? (Godovykh et al. 2023)
Dimension III: The consumer's process of making decisions	Judgments and decision making	How do consumers evaluate deals in the sharing economy? What attributes are distinctive compared to other offers? (So et al. 2019, Tussyadiah & Pesonen 2016) Experimentation to examine the causality and potential interactions among factors involved in SE consumption (Amirkiaee and Evangelopoulos 2018) How consumers use user-generated content in SE decisions (Bae and Koo 2018; Liang et al. 2020) How is the consideration set configured in the SE? (Mody et al. 2019a) How AI techniques are transforming consumers' decisions through SEPs? (Eckhardt et al. 2019, Wirtz et al. 2019) In the decision-making process, decompose service-related effects from platform-related effects (Grüner et al. 2024)
	Post-decision processes	How is the consumer experience influenced by local community and social interaction? (Shuqair et al. 2019, (Tussyadiah 2016) How do consumers respond to negative WOM from SE experiences? (Tadelis 2016) How can SEPs retain customers? Can customers experience opportunistic behaviour by transacting off-platform? (Akhmedova et al. 2020a, Wirtz et al. 2019) Spillover effects of negative reviews (Rifkin et al. 2023) Configuration of services that enhance satisfaction (Lee et al. 2024)
	Innovation issues	How does the disruptive nature of SE services affect consumer decision making? What is the hierarchy of effects in the adoption process of SE service innovations? (Hawlitschek et al. 2018, Yi et al. 2020) Study job crafting in contexts when different degrees of intermediation (Trujillo-Torres et al. 2024) How decisive is the technological component of SE platforms for consumer acceptance? (Cappa et al. 2024)
Dimension IV: Consumer behaviour: Outcomes and issues	Symbolic consumer behaviour	What is the symbolic significance of the consumption of SE brands? Is psychological ownership a typical feeling of the SE? (Davlembayeva et al. 2020c), Fritze et al. 2020) What is the redefinition of the meaning of a brand when the consumer can obtain it through access systems? (Kumar 2024)
	Marketing Ethics and social responsibility	Regulation systems in collaborative communities (Hartl et al. 2016) How SE affects the identity of the community and its legitimacy? Is SE perceived as a constructive or destructive phenomenon? (Gunter et al. 2020) Does the SE benefit all dimensions of sustainability, i.e., economic, environmental and social? (Kumar and Chandra 2024)

5 Theoretical and managerial implications

The collaborative economy blurs the traditional boundaries between consumers and producers as the same individual can play both roles. The distinctive nature of this economic model, in which individuals consume and produce, creating a more participatory and potentially empowering dynamic, has altered consumption norms (Li et al. 2024b), and defined a distinctive customer journey (Trujillo-Torres et al. 2024). Indeed, the SE has become a landmark in CB research by incorporating genuine concepts such as access-based consumption, peer-to-peer interaction, psychological ownership, or liquidity of assets or services (Belk et al. 2019).

From a *building theory perspective*, the present study could serve as a first step toward developing an ontology of CB in the SE, in which all concepts and their relationships with one another are contained and described. Indeed, it can complement the behavioural specificities of SE (Morewedge et al. 2021) by helping to build a model of SE user behaviour linked to the business and management literature. The analysis carried out may help to answer core questions that justify SE as a field of study and that were proposed when it was an emerging issue, such as whether the reputational feedback mechanisms of the sharing economy address the lemons problem (Thierer et al. 2015), or the research questions related to the consumer posited (e.g., Lamberton and Goldsmith 2020; Khalek and Chakraborty 2023). Finally, we provide a roadmap of avenues for further research.

Important *practical implications* can be derived from this review. The emergence of the sharing economy and the lateral markets (e.g. P2P) have meant a rupture in the conventional conception of consumption, in the characteristics of the sharing economy consumer, and a change in the value of the consumer experience (Perren and Kozinets 2018). The user/producer duality of the prosumer extends the role played by psychological and post-purchase processes. For producers, it is critical to understand the motivations of the sharing economy user. Real implementation is not exempt from complexity (Pappas 2019). Motivations have a great influence on the participation of SE and throughout the different consumption processes. Attitudes and especially perceived risk play a decisive role, so it is necessary to develop mechanisms and programmes that provoke positive attitudes and reduce risks (e.g., reputation systems, transparency and verification policies). The research gaps identified should also stimulate debate on the viability of the non-professional and independent model in the face of a growing tendency to link to professional platforms or companies.

For targeting purposes, it is essential to understand the implications of the consumer's cultural profile for the adoption of these products. Psychographics require more attention, especially to understand their role in post-purchase processes (e.g., loyalty). And, though external influences (i.e., reference groups, social influences) show inconclusive findings, the relevance of WOM in decisional processes is clear, the evidence on its consequences is

less well known. Furthermore, new opportunities are available to examine the relevance of symbolism and branding, assessing the implications of branding policies on markets and opportunities for innovation.

6 Conclusions and limitations

This paper is intended to build a bridge between consumer behaviour and business management by focusing on the SE field. To the best of the authors' knowledge, this the first academic work to assess CB domains related to SE by developing a framework-based review. This study organises contributions, yields a number of insights, broadens the understanding of the CB-SE interaction, and provides practical implications. Authors of sharing economy and consumer research fields should readily find a rigorous and comprehensive synthesis of existing research to guide their research. As a cornerstone of the SE literature, CB research encompasses an important corpus of work to understand these changes (Sánchez-Pérez et al. 2021a). The lack of previous works organising the various contributions of CB-related to SE emphasises the inherent diversity of consumer behaviour. Our SLR reviews 459 articles on SE research related to CB, adopting an acknowledged CB framework to structure the analysis.

According to our objectives, we organised, interpreted, and integrated the scattered contributions on BC into Hoyer et al.'s (2017) four dimensions and fourteen domains framework. In general, it should be recognised that research results are heavily mediated by the type of SE industry. Of the four dimensions analysed, consumer's process of make decisions and the psychological core are the dimensions that have attracted the most attention. In contrast, consumer culture and behaviour outcomes, symbolic patterns, ethics, and social responsibility are themes that need to be explored. Even within the former, domains are detected that require more depth, such as the mechanism of memory and knowledge, recognition, and information search. How different types of memory work based on SE stimuli (e.g., imaginery, information to websites, product attributes, episodic memory of SE experiences), the capacities to enhance memory (e.g., recognition, recall) or information processes to help consumers extend their recall of SE brands, and communications remain uncharted. Post-decision feelings have not been sufficiently understood, and there is a need to investigate complaints and response behaviours to negative WOM. The fourth dimension, on consumer behaviour outcomes and specific issues, is the least developed of all. In any case, these are issues that require further analysis, such as identifying patterns of SE use and diffusion, understanding the product life cycle of the SE, compatibility with each consumer's needs, or questions of social relevance, legitimacy, or adaptability in the use of SE. The symbolic meaning of consumption, a key topic in CB, has hardly been studied, with insufficient understanding of the link between culture and SE, its emblematic value, or the role of SE brands.

In addition, most of the work has focused on hospitality and transport. It is necessary to conduct studies in other industries to generalise the results and to learn about the circumstances of other industries.

Furthermore, complementing general review work on the SE (e.g., Khodayari et al. 2025) by focussing on the dimensions of consumer behaviour, our study highlights the most relevant contributions and identifies directions and excited questions that require further research. These research gaps offer promising avenues to advance our understanding of the “prosumer” behaviour, avoiding impressionistic approaches.

Finally, despite its contributions, this work is not without *limitations*. First, this study uses only articles from academic journals that are indexed in the WoS database. Other databases (e.g., Scopus), as well as grey literature, are not included. Second, as in any review task, parameters for inclusion and exclusion of articles may influence the results. And finally, an interpretative qualitative approach was mainly used; therefore, it would be of interest to obtain other quantitative parameters that corroborate the conclusions.

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Data Availability

The data study can be requested from the authors.

Conflict of interest statement

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Electronic supplementary material

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